

Cation-exchange Capacity and Ignition Loss / Moisture Adsorption Study on Five Plastic Fire Clays

M. K. SINHA

Central Glass and Ceramic Research Institute, Calcutta-700 032

Manuscript received 16 July 1990, revised 24 December 1991, accepted 27 January 1992

Clay particles as such are negatively charged. The negative charge is balanced externally by positively charged ions which are exchangeable under suitable conditions. This phenomenon accounts for the property of cation-exchange capacity (C.E.C.) of clays. A knowledge of the C.E.C. is quite helpful in the identification and even estimation of the type of mineral present¹. Physicochemical and thermal properties of clays are also influenced by the amount and nature of exchangeable cations². IL/MA is another simple technique by which the nature and proportion of the clay mineral can be assessed.

The present communication describes the C.E.C. and IL/MA study on five plastic fire clays, namely Mohuamilan (M.C.), Chittorpur (C.C.), Barachatarma (B.C.), Neyveli (N.C.) and Badampahar (B.P.C.), collected from different regions of India. The deposits of M.C. and C.C. are located in Palamau district of Bihar, B.C. is deposited in Purulia district of West Bengal, N.C. and B.P.C. are deposited in South Arcot district, Tamil Nadu and Badampahar district, Orissa respectively. All the five deposits have been reported to be extensive. These plastic clays are used as a bond clay in the ceramic batch composition for it imparts workability and increases dry strength of the body.

Results and Discussion

The cation-exchange capacities of the clays (as received) before and after treatment with H₂O₂ are presented in Table 1. All the clays showed C.E.C. almost within the range given for kaolinite³. The cation-exchange capacities of M.C. and C.C. before treatment with H₂O₂ were 4.0 and 4.2 respectively, and after treatment with H₂O₂ the respective values decreased to 3.2 and 2.8. The low values of C.E.C. of these two clays were due to the fact that their

kaolinite content was comparatively low and the structure was well-ordered⁴ which resulted in coarser size of the clay particles giving rise to lesser number of broken bonds mainly responsible for the C.E.C. of kaolinite. B.C. showed C.E.C. value of 8.2 and this remained unchanged after the treatment with H₂O₂. The relatively high value of this clay was attributed mainly to its high kaolinite content and to some extent, its not having so well-ordered structure⁴. The C.E.C. of N.C. before H₂O₂ treatment was 6.0 and after treatment it was reduced to 5.2. This value was higher than M.C. and C.C. but lower than B.C. The clay content in this case was not as high as that of B.C. and the kaolinite structure was disordered⁴. The C.E.C. values of B.P.C. before and after H₂O₂ treatment were 10.8 and 10.0 respectively. Though the kaolinite content of this clay was lower than N.C. and B.C., the value was higher than all the clays. The kaolinite was very disordered and mixed with small amount of illite⁴ in this clay which accounted for the higher value of C.E.C.

The distribution of exchangeable cations are listed in Table 1. The predominant exchangeable cation in all the clays was calcium. In case of M.C. and B.C., the sum total of the exchangeable cations was less than the cation-exchange capacity indicating that part of the exchangeable cation⁵ was H⁺. In case of other three clays, the sum total of the exchangeable cations exceeded the cation-exchange capacity. This could be explained by supposing that calcium acted partly as the monovalent ion [CaOH]⁺ and so its average effective equivalent weight lay in the range⁶ 20–40.

IL and MA values of the clays (<1 μ fraction) are given in Table 2. Kaolinite clays have low MA values, sepiolite and montmorillonite high values, and illites are intermediate. Ignition-loss shows the opposite trend to moisture adsorption, being high

TABLE 1—CATION-EXCHANGE CAPACITY AND EXCHANGEABLE CATIONS OF CLAYS

Clay	Cation-exchange capacity equiv /100 g		Exchangeable cations equiv /100 g					Total exchangeable cations
	Before H ₂ O ₂ treatment	After H ₂ O ₂ treatment	Na	K	Ca	Mg		
	M.C.	4.0	3.2	0.92	0.04	1.97	0.31	
C.C.	4.2	2.8	0.88	0.10	4.41	0.60	5.99	
B.C.	8.2	8.2	0.41	0.07	4.02	1.21	5.71	
N.C.	6.0	5.2	0.93	0.18	3.07	2.57	6.75	
B.P.C.	10.8	10.0	0.90	0.19	6.92	5.31	13.34	

TABLE 2—IL/MA VALUES OF CLAYS (<1 μ FRACTION)

Clay	% Loss on ignition at 1000°	% Loss on ignition at 375°	% Ignition loss (IL)	% Moisture adsorption (MA)	IL/MA
M.C.	13.45	1.02	12.43	1.02	12.19
C.C.	13.42	1.42	12.00	1.00	12.00
B.C.	17.78	1.61	16.14	1.86	8.68
N.C.	16.79	2.71	14.08	4.37	3.22
B.P.C.	15.34	4.74	10.63	7.71	1.37

for kaolinites and low for montmorillonites with illite again occupying an intermediate position. The moisture adsorption (MA) values of the samples under study were in the range 1.00–7.71. This indicated that all the clays belonged to kaolinite group and the differences in values were mainly due to the degree of orderness and the presence of other clay minerals. The ignition loss (IL) values of the samples varied from 10.60 to 16.14. IL/MA values of the clays were in the range 1.37–12.19. IL/MA ratios of M.C. and C.C. indicated that they were well-ordered kaolinite followed by B.C. Comparatively lower values of N.C. and B.P.C. were mainly due to kaolinite of disordered nature.

Experimental

Removal of organic matter: In order to remove the organic matter of the clays, all the clay samples were treated⁷ with 10% H₂O₂ and warmed on a hot-plate maintained at low temperature for 72 h, then washed with distilled water and dried.

Separation of <1 μ fraction of clays: To obtain the <1 μ fraction of clays, a sedimentation process based on Stokes' law was utilised with concentrated ammonia as deflocculant. The technique entailed syphoning a suspension at a pre-determined time and at a fixed height and this process was repeated for 4–5 days⁸.

Cation-exchange capacity. Ammonium acetate method: The sample (0.5 g; –200 mesh) was treated with excess of N-NH₄OAc (pH 7.0), the excess being removed by repeated washing with alcohol. After the clay was distilled over MgO,

the liberated ammonia was absorbed in boric acid solution and titrated against standard solution of H₂SO₄. The cation-exchange capacity was then calculated from the titre value.

Distribution of exchangeable cations: The sample (20 g; –200 mesh) washed with alcohol to remove the soluble salt, was leached with excess of N-NH₄OAc and the leachate was analysed. Na and K were estimated by a EEL 100 flame photometer, and Ca and Mg by Perkin-Elmer 372 atomic absorption spectrophotometer.

Ignition loss/moisture adsorption: The method has been described by Keeling⁹ and consists of determining the ignition loss of the clay mineral (IL) and its capacity for moisture adsorption under standard conditions (M.A.).

Acknowledgement

The author is thankful to Director, C.G. & C.R.I., Calcutta, for his kind permission to publish this paper.

References

1. M. BHARADWAJ, B. M. BISHUI and D. K. GHOSH, *Central Glass Cer Res Inst. Bull.*, 1971, **18**, 75; F. Q. ALKHALISSI and W. E. WORRALL, *Trans. Br. Cer. Soc.*, 1982, **81**, 145
2. R. E. GRIM, "Clay Mineralogy", Mc-Graw-Hill, New York, 1953, p. 364; N. K. MITRA, D. DAS and R. K. MANDAL, *Trans. Br. Cer. Soc.*, 1977, **76**, 108; P. PRABHAKARAM, *Trans. Br. Cer. Soc.*, 1963, **67**, 105.
3. R. E. GRIM, "Clay Mineralogy", Mc-Graw-Hill, New York, 1953, p. 129.
4. M. K. SINHA and S. K. GUHA, *Trans. Indian Cer. Soc.*, 1990, **49**, 100.
5. H. V. OLFPHEN and J. J. FRIPIAT, "Data Handbook for Clay Materials and other Non-metallic Minerals", Pergamon, New York, 1979, p. 195.
6. W. E. WORRALL, *Trans. Br. Cer. Soc.*, 1963, **62**, 477
7. S. M. GRIFFITH and M. SCHNITZER, *Can. J. Soil Sci.*, 1977, **57**, 223.
8. R. N. YONG and B. P. WARKENTIN, "Soil Properties and Behaviours", Elsevier, New York, 1975, p. 11.
9. P. S. KEELING, *Trans. Br. Cer. Soc.*, 1961, **60**, 217.